

APPROACHES TO THE FORMATION OF WRITING SKILLS AMONG FOREIGN NON-PHILOLOGICAL STUDENTS

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Annotation: The article describes some methodological issues of teaching foreign students to write and substantiates the relevance of the formation of writing skills at the initial stage of education. The aspects of the formation of the ability to correctly write individual words, terms, phrases, sentences, etc. are considered, which contributes to meeting the communicative needs of students in terms of educational and professional communication and organizing further independent work to improve writing skills.

Keywords: oral speech, written speech, types of writing, skills and abilities, learning goals, writing technique.

The aim of the work was to identify the problems of teaching writing in Russian as a non-native language in groups with English as the language of instruction, as well as to describe the communicative needs of this contingent of students in terms of educational and professional communication. When creating a written message, the key role belongs to the exercise, i.e. creating ideas about what will be written before the moment of writing. These are the levels of inner speech, which manifests itself in the form of hidden speech-motor reactions, they are accompanied by auditory and

visual representations of words. Internal speech is not accompanied by vocalization, but has its own grammatical and stylistic structure, as well as a specific speech technique. The level of external written speech is a form of graphic fixation of internal speech. The complex phenomenon of writing includes the skills of: writing letter signs (calligraphy); correct transcoding of speech sounds into adequate writing signs (spelling); construction and design of a written statement (composition); lexical and grammatical skills. All of the above indicates the specifics of the goals and objectives of teaching writing.

The goals of teaching writing are closely related to the overall purpose and objectives of the process of learning a new language. However, in the field of only one type of speech activity – writing – there may be quite a lot of such tasks and it is not always possible to specify the tasks that language learners will have to solve in real life. Therefore, for example, in the educational field, it is more useful to identify tasks that: language learners should learn to perform as language users (correctly write their name, addressee's name, date, address; write congratulations, a personal letter having a scheme for building "Russian

writing"; to provide information about yourself, your family, city, interests, to request the same information from your addressee, to provide basic personal information in the questionnaire, form (at the hotel); to make personal notes during reading, listening (extracts, records); to describe events facts, phenomena and comment on them; write a job application and perform other formalities in writing, etc.); are an immediate part of the educational process (drawing up a plan, talking points, recording the collection of educational and subject information, the compilation of "educational records, the creation of annotations, summaries, abstracts, writing out information from reference literature, etc.). The set of goals and objectives allows you to choose

an adequate approach to teaching writing. There are at least two approaches in the methodology of teaching foreign languages related to the teaching of productive (also called expressive) written speech. One of them is based on the psychological

characteristics of the generation of a written statement. In this case, the creative process of speech generation, the personality of the writer, his communicative and

cognitive needs, target settings for the upcoming types of written messages, analysis of the audience to which the written speech is addressed occupy a central place in the organization of writing training. A writing learning model based on the psycholinguistic theory of the generation of written statements includes three stages: 1) training in planning, programming the content of a written message;

2) training in the implementation of the ide of a written statement: training in structuring a written message, mastering the rhetorical

organization and composition of the text;

3) training in self-control, editing written.

The second approach focuses on the product of speech activity – a written statement, a text, a speech work, while the object of mastery is the form and organization of written discourse. A distinctive feature of this approach is that the development of productive (expressive) written speech is closely related to the receptive form of written communication – reading. As a result, writing skills are correlated with different types of reading by:

a) writing out certain information, judgments, arguments, conclusions;

b) writing the main facts of the text;

c) making a summary;

d) writing down your own opinion about what you read . In the process of interconnected learning, the following skills are formed:

- 1) the ability to convey the basic information of the read / listened text;
- 2) the ability to convey the main idea;
- 3) the ability to briefly / in detail compare, compare the described facts;
- 4) the ability to provide illustrative examples, arguments;
- 5) the ability to review, combine, combine information;
- 6) the ability to characterize, express an assessment, own attitude to what is being stated (agreement – disagreement, approval – disapproval, censure, surprise, etc.);
- 7) the ability to present information abstractly, annotate and summarize it, etc.

This approach to teaching writing is conventionally called textual, it is well developed in the methodology of teaching both native and foreign languages. A typical scheme of work in teaching coherent productive writing is as follows: from analyzing the sample text (with a gradual decrease in reliance on the sample) to creating an independent written message. In the textual approach, writing training includes several stages: reading, comprehension and analysis of texts. Depending on the didactic task separately or a comprehensive linguistic, semantic stylistic, compositional analysis of the text is carried out; the construction of an utterance by analogy with the sample text; the writing of independent written messages. In teaching Russian as a foreign language, it is possible to combine the possibilities of these approaches in a balanced way, depending on the level of language proficiency and the needs of students. The method of teaching writing is differentiated depending on the stage of learning a non-native, new language. Russian Russian alphabet, to master the rules of Russian graphics, spelling, etc. In order to form skills and abilities in the field of reproductive and productive writing, the student needs to master the technique of writing, i.e. get acquainted with the Russian alphabet, master the rules of Russian graphics, spelling, punctuation. Thus, learning the writing technique is the initial stage of learning to write, and step –by-step mastering it, as evidenced by the experience of working in groups with the English language of instruction, is the key to the successful formation of writing skills. The introduction to the Russian alphabet takes place within the framework of an introductory phonetic and grammatical course.

Students get acquainted with the sounds of the Russian language and the letters denoting these sounds (printed and handwritten, uppercase and lowercase). In printed form, uppercase letters, as you know, differ from lowercase letters in height, and in handwritten form they differ both in size and in outline, which may pose a certain difficulty for a person who has started learning a new language for him. Sequence

The study of Russian letters depends, on the one hand, on the difficulty of the sound they denote; on the other, on the difficulty of spelling the letter itself for students of a certain nationality. For example, those students who speak Cyrillic or Latin writing in their native language can easily master the spelling of Russian letters. Hindus, Arabs and representatives of other nationalities who use Indian, Arabic, and hieroglyphic writing in their writing face significant difficulties in such cases. Deviations may occur. They may be associated with an increase in the size of lowercase letters and a decrease in the height of uppercase letters, with the writing of the letters "k", "l" above the line (the interfering influence of the Latin alphabet: k, l), with disregard for the inclination characteristic of Russian writing. At the same time, some violations, according to the methodologists, are quite acceptable, since they do not impede written communication. The formation of skills in graphic and calligraphic design of a written text consists of a number of interrelated operations: sound representation, sound and visual perception, association of sounds with corresponding graphemes, hand-motor activity combined with internal speech.

Difficulties associated with mastering graphics and calligraphy are explained, in addition to the mismatches of alphabets in the native and Russian languages, by a number of reasons: the discrepancy in all languages of sounds and letters: in many cases Russian is also characterized by the designation of a number of sounds with one letter (good) and several letters of one sound (laugh); the so-called polysemy of graphemes (mushroom flu); the presence of synonymous letter designations: ts-ts-ts; the presence in the native and Russian languages of the same the spelling of letters that convey different sounds: c,n, p,m; the presence in the Russian language of letters with superscript and subscript elements, the spelling of which is mixed: v-u, e-V. It has been established that at the initial stage of learning to write, more than half of the errors are the result of poor assimilation of Russian phonetics, therefore, sufficient attention should be paid to letter-to-letter correspondences, since the writer always starts from the audible word and its pronunciation. In our opinion, exercises of the following nature are especially effective in groups with

the English language of instruction: sound-letter and syllabic analysis of words; auditory exercises; cheating with simultaneous execution of additional tasks (underlining of certain graphemes, by restoring letters missing in a word); grouping words according to certain characteristics (two- and three-syllable words with emphasis on a certain syllable; writing numbers in words; writing out words from the text related to the same topic, etc.); constructing words from letters and syllables. The basic principle of Russian spelling is morphological; which means that each morpheme (prefix, root, suffix) is written the same way, although depending on phonetic conditions it is pronounced differently (water – water). Based on this, in groups with English. The language of instruction justifies the use of exercises of various word-formation analysis, especially medical terms, which students will encounter during practice in clinical settings. In our opinion, when working with this category of students, it is possible not to take into account that the spelling of some words is subject to the phonetic principle (they are written as they are pronounced: without a name, arose, restore), and in writing other words, the law of tradition sometimes wins (as it was written before; this concerns the letter "g" in the endings of adjectives (new), the letters "b" at the end of the verbs (do), the letters "a" and "o" in the same root morpheme (to sunbathe, but tan)). In other languages, there are also principles of writing words. So, the historical principle of writing is typical for English and French, which makes it difficult to form spelling skills, requires memorizing words by heart. In German, as in Russian, a number of principles are combined: phonetic, semantic (hieroglyphic) with the dominance of morphological. The rules of Russian spelling are given as you become familiar with the corresponding word or grammatical form. Overcoming difficulties is facilitated by working on the composition of the word, various kinds of spelling dictation, self-dictation, as well as special exercises: a) copying the text (copying) in order to learn

the rules of spelling; b) copying, complicated by additional tasks (filling in gaps,

underlining certain letters, etc.); c) grouping words (homographs, thematically related Words, words similar in composition, etc.); d) writing dictation against the background of noise or other interference, etc. Written speech differs from oral speech in its completeness, extreme clarity, and fullness. These characteristic differences are especially noticeable in the speech of native speakers or students at an advanced stage of education. In the practice of learning Russian as a foreign language, one of the most important tasks is to

teach foreign students the perception and recording of speech by ear – in terms of preparing students for listening and recording lectures. Recording speech perceived by ear refers to secondary types of communication activities. It is a rather complicated process even in the field of the native language. When teaching foreign students in groups with the English language of learning to perceive and record speech by ear, we are faced with the need for special selection and organization of educational material, special organization of the educational process. The most common exercises in teaching writing are dictation, exposition, and essays. In our work in groups with English as the language of instruction, based on the limited amount of study time and the Russian language program, we pay attention to one of the types of written work, namely dictation. Dictation in all its variety of forms (vocabulary, selective, phrasal, free, creative, self-dictation) makes it possible for foreign students to develop, in addition to graphic, spelling and grammatical skills, also a set of additional skills necessary for writing lectures on the specialty: a) fluent writing skills; b) the skill of using linguistic means of speech, perceived by ear; c) the skill of quickly recording the main content of the listened segment of speech; d) the skill of shortening words and sentences (syntactic condensation); e) the skill of independently constructing

a phrase, a small finished statement.

Conclusion

The material for dictation is educational texts from textbooks on the specialty and popular science texts, the choice of which is determined by the goals and objectives facing students and teachers in each case. Positive results are achieved by observing the conditions of systematic dictation with a gradual complication of lexical and grammatical material, an increase in the volume of dictation and the pace of speech, creating at each stage of the development of the skill of recording speech from hearing an optimal mode in which the pace of speech of the speaker and listeners would coincide.

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